

Potentiometric Study of the Oxidation of Sulphate by Alkaline Ferricyanide

S. S. OJHA and R. K. PRASAD

Physical Chemistry Laboratory, L. S. College, Muzaffarpur (Bihar) & Chemical Laboratory, Rajendra College, Chapra (Bihar)

Manuscript received 18 June 1971; revised 16 February 1972 accepted 20 September 1972

The oxidation of sulphite by alkaline ferricyanide has been followed potentiometrically using both platinum and gold electrodes. The reaction is quantitative, and hence analytically significant, if the mixtures are heated and stored for a considerable length of time. At lower alkali concentrations the oxidation proceeds via sulphur (V) species through single electron transfer steps.

ON the basis of the Latimer's table¹ of E^0 values, the oxidation of sulphite with alkaline ferricyanide would be expected to be quantitative. Vepreksiska *et al.*³ reported that with inert complexes the product formed is only sulphate while with labile complexes³ both sulphate and dithionate are formed. The reaction rate decreases with decreasing pH^4 . According to Singh and Malik⁵ the first step of this reaction is a complementary one equivalent process.

The present work constitutes a potentiometric investigation to ascertain whether the reaction involves successive one electron steps or a single two electron step.

Experimental

M/50 solutions of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ (G.R.) with different concentrations of caustic soda were prepared in air-free freshly distilled water. M/50 solutions of anhydrous (Analar) sodium sulphite with different concentrations of caustic soda were also prepared in air-free double distilled water.

Potentiometric titrations were carried in cells which had, on one side, bright thick platinum wire cleaned with (N) NaOH followed by 6N HNO_3 and finally heated in alcohol flame. The other side was saturated calomel electrode. Electroplated gold⁶ electrodes were also used in place of platinum electrodes. In each cell 10 mls. of the sulphite solution were taken. Varying amounts of the oxidant were added to the cells. The reactions were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. Reaction mixtures were stored at room temperature from 24 to 72 hr as indicated in the tables 1 and 2 and e.m.f.'s were taken at the end of the period. Some reaction mixtures after 24 hr of storage at room temperature were heated for 6 hr at about 70° and e.m.f.'s were taken. The reverse titration was also done in nitrogen free atmosphere. Some typical curves are shown in the figure. RT in the tables means Room Temperatures.

TABLE 1

Cell : 5 ml of 0.02M Sodium sulphite solution
Titrant : 0.02005M Potassium ferricyanide solution
Medium : Sodium hydroxide (Nitrogen atmosphere)

Concentration of talkali	Temp., °C/ Period of storage (hr)	Inflexions in ml of oxidant	Moles of oxidant per mole of reductant
N/20	RT/24	5.0	1.0025
		9.6	1.9250
	RT/72	5.0	1.0025
		9.8	1.9560
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	1.0025
		10.0	2.0050
N	RT/24	5.0	1.0025
		9.8	1.9650
	RT/72	5.0	1.0025
		9.8	1.9650
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	5.0	1.0025
		10.0	2.0050
2N	RT/24	9.8	1.9650
	RT/72	9.9	1.9850
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	10.0	2.0050
4N	RT/24	9.8	1.9650
	RT/72	10.0	2.0050
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	10.0	2.0050

RT = room temperature

Results and Discussion

Qualitatively the reaction is slow, becoming slower in low concentrations of alkali. Potentials are stabilised after comparatively longer periods, the bright platinum electrode providing a relatively smoother curve. In each case when alkali concentrations are high ($> N$) only one sharp inflexion occurs corresponding to the stoichiometry,

TABLE 2

Cell : 5 ml of 0.02005M Potassium ferricyanide solution
 Titrant : 0.02M Sodium sulphite solution
 Medium : Sodium hydroxide (Nitrogen atmosphere)

Concentration of alkali	Temp., °C/ Period of storage (hr)	Inflexions in ml of reductant	Moles of reductant per mole of oxidant
N/20	RT/24	2.7	0.54
	RT/72	2.6	0.52
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	2.5	0.50
N	RT/24	2.5	0.50
	RT/72	2.5	0.50
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	2.5	0.50
2N	RT/24	2.5	0.50
	RT/72	2.5	0.50
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	2.5	0.50
4N	RT/24	2.5	0.50
	RT/72	2.5	0.50
	70, 6 hr; RT/120	2.5	0.50

whether ferricyanide is added to the sulphite or *vice versa*. This happens when the reaction mixtures are heated and stored for a considerable length of time. At lower alkali concentrations, an additional inflexion occurs at the one equivalent step,

In *N* alkali this inflexion is reduced just to a peak in the curve at the point corresponding to equation (2). With gold electrode, only one inflexion point is detected under all conditions, the reasons not being clear at this stage.

From these observations we conclude that the reaction proceeds by one equivalent steps leading to successive formations, quantitatively, of dithionate (formed by dimerisation of SO_3^- ions) and sulphate ions which may not be realised experimentally unless the alkali concentration is low ($< N$).

When sulphite is added to ferricyanide, the curves, after the point of inflexion, are marked with frequent rise and fall which may be attributed to the formation of Fe(II) in its different forms with different redox potentials.

Fig. 1

AA' & BB' represent gradual additions of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ to 10 mls of Na_2SO_3 solutions in 4N and N/20 NaOH media respectively; CC' represent reverse titrations.

O : readings with Pt electrode;
 X : readings with Au electrode.

By the end of the titration period (72 hr) the gold film of the gold electrode appears to be visibly dissolved. This is attributed to the reaction of the gold with ferrocyanide in presence of atmospheric oxygen.⁷

References

1. LATIMER, "Oxidation Potentials", 4th ed. (1959).
2. J. VEPREKSIKA and D. M. WAGNEROVA, Through *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **62**, 15747(a).
3. J. VEPREKSIKA *et al.*, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1966, **31**(3), 1248.
4. J. VEPREKSIKA, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1966, **31**(8), 3287.
5. B. SINGH and I. I. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 435.
6. STROUTES, GILFILLAN and WILSON, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, Oxford, Clarendon Press (1955).
7. SNEED, MAYNARD and BRATED, *Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry*, p. 215.